

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROBLEM-BASED EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING CLINICAL REASONING SKILLS WHILE TEACHING BIOETHICS TO STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing development of socio-economic spheres in our republic, further improvement of the quality of personnel training in the system of higher and secondary specialized education; enhancing students' inquisitiveness, creativity, thinking abilities, and speech culture in vocational training based on modern achievements in science and technology; purposeful and effective use of information and communication technologies in mastering the intricacies of professions; and developing students' skills for independent work are among the most pressing issues of today. In modern educational settings, developing future specialists' abilities for independent learning and creative problem-solving is of great importance in forming their professional skills. These characteristics are cultivated through enhancing students' capacity for independent thinking and activating their knowledge acquisition processes. The educational process is organized in such a way as to increase the consciousness and activity of learners, ensuring that students consciously and actively acquire scientific knowledge and methods of its practical application. This approach aims to develop creative initiative and independence in educational activities, as well as enhance thinking and speech skills among students.

Keywords: clinical risk, bioethical reasoning.

Bernard Shaw once said, "If you try to teach a person something, they will never learn anything." For a learner to properly assimilate the material, they must actively work on it. Simply listening or skimming through it is not enough. The learner needs to reflect on the material, discuss it thoroughly, or complete an independent assignment related to the topic. The learner can achieve their intended goal through independent and creative activities such as observing, comparing, identifying differences, and generalizing objects, processes, and phenomena. Therefore, even in teaching subjects, the learners' knowledge acquisition and learning activities do not become active on their own; they primarily arise as a result of mental

and conscious engagement. Before activating the learning activities of students, it is crucial to analyze their initial level of knowledge, their ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice, their skills, and their capacity for independent work. Without a comprehensive analysis of these characteristics, it is impossible to assess the level of active engagement that students can demonstrate. Therefore, studying active learning methods aimed at enhancing students' educational-cognitive and educational-practical activities, determining their place and role in the system of pedagogical technologies, and developing methodologies for their application in the educational process is considered one of today's urgent tasks. Regarding the concept of method in the education system, its meaning is the most precise and shortest way to achieve the intended learning objective. In research, a method is defined as a consciously chosen path or approach to achieve goals such as solving a problem, obtaining results from an experiment, or studying and teaching a subject.

In some pedagogical literature, the word "method" is also used interchangeably with the term "method." For instance, method (derived from the Greek word "methodos," meaning a way of searching or knowing, theory, or doctrine) is defined as a collection of operations or approaches for practical or theoretical assimilation of reality, subordinated to solving a specific task. In recent times, the term "active forms and methods of education" has become widely used in pedagogical practice. It encompasses a group of pedagogical technologies that ensure a high level of student learning activity. In recent times, another term has become widely used - "interactive learning." The term "Interactive Learning" in English denotes education based on active engagement with the subject of education (teacher, trainer, leader, manager). Essentially, it represents one of the variants (models) of communicative technology. In other words, interactive learning consists of a highly organized collaborative relationship between the object and subject of education, based on mutual two-way (reciprocal) exchange of information between them.

The teaching method is the regulated organization of collaborative activities between the teacher and student to guarantee the achievement of set educational goals. Without active learning methods, it is difficult to achieve the intended learning objectives, activate the learning process, and attain educational outcomes. The implementation of such active methods by the teacher encourages students to work hard, captures their attention, prompts them to work independently on self-improvement, stimulates thinking and research, increases their interest in lessons, and enhances their participation. We consider activation as one of the

main factors aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. Activation comes from the Latin word meaning "active" or "industrious," and refers to the ability to enhance a person's knowledge acquisition and teaching capabilities by strengthening their intellect and willpower. By active learning, we understand a set of factors that promote the conscious and active participation of students and teachers in the educational process, as well as develop their independent and creative abilities.

The overall activity of the learner refers to their efforts aimed at acquiring knowledge and skills, as well as comprehending the essence of processes and phenomena. Through this active engagement, the knowledge, skills, and abilities formed become the learner's "personal property," enabling them to apply this knowledge whenever needed.

Initial research has shown that activating learners creates opportunities for:

- establishing conscious relationships between educators and learners;
- developing learners' independent and free thinking abilities;
- enabling learners to work independently with information sources;
- ensuring regular and full participation of learners in classes;
- awakening interest in learning;

The more a teacher can evoke pleasant emotional impressions in learners, the more their engagement increases in the process of mastering new educational material.

It should be emphasized that for successful teaching, at each stage of the learner's process of acquiring knowledge, skills, and abilities, the teacher stimulates and organizes their active conscious thinking.

Consciousness primarily involves the learner's understanding of the educational objectives they need to achieve, as well as comprehending the content of the material being studied and the tasks they must manage. Moreover, consciousness implies that the learner does not merely memorize the educational material mechanically or perform tasks robotically. Instead, they should be able to explain the rationale behind completing a task in a particular way. Through their responses to the teacher's questions, learners can demonstrate that they truly grasp the meaning of the educational material being studied.

Consciousness also reflects the learner's responsible attitude towards completing assignments. A consciously thinking and working learner strives to complete any educational task accurately and on time. In necessary cases, they aim to complete the task independently, relying on the assistance of teachers or talented students when needed. Consciousness also

reflects the learner's responsible attitude towards completing assignments. A consciously thinking and working learner strives to complete any educational task accurately and on time. When necessary, they aim to complete the task independently, relying on the assistance of teachers or more capable students when needed. In research studies, activating students' educational and cognitive activities is frequently emphasized as one of the crucial tasks of the learning process. Rational and effective organization of the educational process, incorporating modern teaching methods and international experiences, not only enhances lesson effectiveness but also develops students' scientific and intellectual potential and their ability to think independently.

According to A.M. Matyushkin, active cognition emerges as a result of systematically and sequentially assigning tasks and creating problem situations in the educational process. Since activity arises from consciousness, this circumstance also necessitates the coordination of content, form, methods, and means of studying sciences. When determining the level of activity, it is necessary to consider the complexity level of the educational material. Psychological and pedagogical issues arise in activating learners' knowledge acquisition and learning activities. This is because psychologists view the activity of learners in acquiring knowledge and learning as a psychological characteristic, while educators consider it the main principle and modern requirement of the educational process.

To increase the learning and cognitive activity of students, the teacher should develop various forms and methods of conducting classes, depending on the level of complexity of the educational material.

The following levels of activity are presented in research.

The first level of activity is manifested in the process of students repeating previously acquired knowledge, restoring it in memory, following the teacher's direct guidance and instructions, or performing specific tasks based on a given example. Because the students' recall of the studied theoretical material serves to recall their actions aimed at finding solutions to problems of production content corresponding to it based on the example.

The second level of activity requires understanding the essence of the studied object or process, involving elements of creative thinking to a certain extent. This level of activity entails identifying similarities and differences in the studied objects and processes, as well as applying acquired knowledge in modified situations and conditions.

The third level of activity demands creative actions. It demonstrates creative activity aimed at achieving the intended learning objective. Partially exploratory activity fully transforms into a creative nature. At this level of activity, the acquired knowledge is systematic, deep, and thorough, allowing for its application in any desired situation.

The level of activation is determined, firstly, by the degree to which students are motivated to study the educational material and their capacity for independent work and research. Secondly, it depends on the conditions created by the teacher to stimulate the teaching and learning process, as well as the form and active methods of education and didactic tools employed.

Conclusion: One of the main factors in effectively achieving learning outcomes is the widespread use of active teaching methods. These methods develop students' ability to think freely and independently, make autonomous decisions in various problem situations, and ensure their active participation in the educational process. Active teaching methods create opportunities for students to think freely and independently during the learning process, fostering a creative environment in classes and increasing student engagement. In this approach, the teacher's role shifts from being a transmitter of ready-made knowledge to becoming a facilitator and advisor, creating conditions for students to independently acquire knowledge.

List of References

1. Narzieva N.N. Formation of research skills based on core competencies in general education school students: Ped. science. (PhD) diss. - Samarkand, 2019. - 174 p.
2. Nurtazin S.T., Bazarbayev Zh.M., Yesimsitova Z.B., Yermekbayeva D.K. Innovative method of "problem-oriented learning" // Achievements of modern natural science. - 2013. - No. 5. - P. 112-114.
3. Pedagogy: Encyclopedia. Volume II / Compiled by a team. - Tashkent: State Scientific Publishing House "Uzbekistan National Encyclopedia," 2015. - 376 p.
4. Amrilloevich I.A. Cognitive competence as a key factor in the continuous professional development of a teacher // . - 2022. - Vol. 49. - No. 01.
5. Barrows H.S. Problem-based learning in medicine and beyond: A brief overview // New directions of teaching and learning. - 1996. - No. 68. - P. 3-12.
6. Chan Lin L.J. Technology integration applied to project-based learning in science. // Innovations in Education and Teaching International. - 2008. - 45 (1). - P. 55-65.

7. David J.L. What research says about ... project-based learning // Educational Leadership. - 2008. - 65 (5), - P. 80-82.
8. Desabie J. La Mobilite Sociale en France // Bulletin d'Information. - 1956. - P. 25-63.
9. Doppelt Y. Implementation and assessment of project-based learning in a flexible environment // International Journal of Technology and Design Education. - 2003. - No. 13. - P. 255-272.
10. Gultekin M. The effect of project-based learning on learning outcomes in the 5th-grade social studies course in primary education // Educational Science. - 2005. - 5 (2). - P. 548-556.